

LEARNING RESOURCE CENTERS: SCHOOLS' INITIATIVES AND CHALLENGES

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to assess the initiatives, support, and challenges in the establishment and sustainability of Learning Resource Centers (LRCs) in public elementary schools across the three congressional districts of Bohol during the school year 2024–2025. Employing a qualitative research design, the study gathered data through interviews and focus group discussions with school supervisors, principals, and teachers. Thematic analysis was used to categorize responses into major themes that addressed the schools' initiatives, internal and external stakeholder support, encountered challenges, and proposed measures for improvement. Findings revealed that despite financial limitations, schools demonstrated proactive efforts to develop LRCs, often repurposing unused spaces and launching community-driven resource mobilization initiatives. Support from parents, alumni, local government units, and non-government organizations proved crucial in sustaining LRC operations. However, challenges such as outdated materials, limited digital resources, and inadequate space continued to hinder LRC effectiveness. Respondents recommended practical strategies including local fundraising, digital resource integration, stakeholder engagement, and structured LRC management systems. The study concludes that the development and sustainability of LRCs require collaborative efforts, innovative solutions, and continuous evaluation. These findings serve as a valuable basis for educational leaders and policymakers to design programs and policies that enhance LRC services and improve the overall quality of education in public schools.

Keywords: *Learning Resource Centers, Stakeholder Support, Educational Facilities, Public Schools, Resource Mobilization, LRC Challenges*

INTRODUCTION

The Learning Resource Center (LRC) is one of the important facilities in the school in shaping learners' thinking and deeper understanding of their subjects beyond the classroom (Smith, 2001). Based on this, the learning resource centers of the schools form the foundation for the process of self-learning in which learners acquire new knowledge through their own efforts. Selvaratnam (2008) states that the learning resource center is a self-learning device and in today's educational world, and it is necessary to increase the amount of time that learners engage in independent learning.

Furthermore, learning resource centers help learners develop critical thinking, organize information, and discover new ones (Jones, 2018). This emphasizes that LRC acts as a place that provides opportunities which foster a culture of research and knowledge sharing among learners (Brown, 2016). Nowadays, with the development of technology, modern devices to search for knowledge, to update knowledge and to provide what students need when they need it, learning resource should be found.

While the Learning Resource Center (LRC) is a vital asset for public elementary school teachers and learners, several gaps still exist that limit its effectiveness (Canales & Maldonado, 2018). One significant gap is the inadequate availability of up-to-date and relevant resources. Many LRCs in public schools struggle with outdated textbooks, insufficient digital resources, and a lack of materials tailored to the specific needs of learners in remote areas. Finally, the funding and support from local or national governments may limit the ability of these centers to expand their offerings and improve their services in the utilization of learning resource center in the public schools. The physical infrastructure of some public schools in the Philippines remains substandard, characterized by limited space, poor internet connectivity, and insufficient technological resources to support modern teaching and learning methods (Navarro, 2022).

Recent studies have emphasized that improving access to quality educational resources is crucial to ensuring better learning outcomes. Parojenog and Pabalan (2024) concluded that several factors contribute to the quality of public basic education in the Philippines, including the application of differentiated instruction, the use of diverse pedagogical approaches, and the provision of appropriate and sufficient instructional materials to both teachers and students. They asserted that quality education is assured when schools focus on continuous improvement and the strategic use of educational resources — a commitment that directly aligns with the proper establishment and development of effective learning resource centers.

Meanwhile, with the years of experience in academic settings, the researcher's dedication to student growth has cultivated a deep commitment to providing high-quality education, but this commitment extends beyond the classroom. It necessitates a holistic

approach that considers the needs of individual learners and provides them with the resources and support they require to succeed. In essence, they are tangible expressions of the researcher's commitment to nurturing students beyond the confines of the traditional classroom.

Moreover, having spent considerable time in academe, the researcher remains passionate about empowering students to become critical thinkers, prepared to face the challenges they may encounter along the way. As an educational management student, it is evident that DepEd policymakers, supervisors, and principals should prioritize the establishment of Learning Resource Centers (LRCs) or libraries in every public school to address the specific academic needs of students, particularly in subjects that are challenging for them. These educational leaders must take proactive steps to ensure that LRCs are adequately developed and resourced, so they can effectively support student learning and achievement. In pursuit of this goal, the researcher is interested in investigating the initiatives, support and challenges status of learning resource centers in all public elementary schools across the three districts of Bohol.

This study is intended to serve as a basis for the government to facilitate funding for the establishment of learning resource centers in all public elementary schools across the province of Bohol. The goal is to enhance the quality of education for all students.

Research Questions

This study aimed to assess the initiatives, support, and challenges of Learning Resource Centers (LRCs) of public schools in the three districts of the province of Bohol in the school year 2024-2025.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What are the schools' initiation in the development as perceived by school administrators?
2. What internal and external support received from stakeholders in the development of LRC?
3. What challenges were encountered in the development of LRC?
4. What do respondents (supervisors, principals and teachers) recommend to enhance LRC services?
5. What improvement measures may be proposed to enhance Learning Resource Center (LRC) services in every school?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This research employed a qualitative approach. The qualitative method was used to assess the status of the initiatives, support, and challenges of Learning Resource

Centers (LRCs), as well as to gather insights into the perceptions of respondents regarding the usefulness and deficiencies of LRCs. School administrators such as principals, head teachers, and school-in-charge personnel were randomly selected to participate and were individually interviewed, with a request to respond truthfully. The researcher relied on the respondents' honesty and objectivity in answering the interview questions. The interview responses were then analyzed and collated to generate clearer findings, which informed the conclusions and provided recommendations for enhancing learning programs.

Research Environment

The study was conducted in the three (3) districts of Bohol, specifically in the following towns: Cortes, Maribojoc, Balilihan, Catigbian, and Loon in the First District; Trinidad, Ubay, San Miguel, Talibon, and Trinidad in the Second District; and Jagna, Duero, Garcia Hernandez, Guindulman, and Mabini in the Third District. The research focused on five (5) schools in each town that had Learning Resource Center (LRC) facilities, excluding those established solely through government provision. These schools were purposively selected due to their accessibility, particularly in terms of transportation convenience for the researcher.

Research Respondents

The study employed a purposive sampling technique to select respondents from schools where Learning Resource Centers (LRCs) were established. This method was chosen to ensure the inclusion of individuals who possessed specific characteristics relevant to the research questions. The participants consisted of 15 school principals, 15 school heads, and 15 school-in-charge personnel from the three congressional districts of Bohol.

Distribution of Respondents

Areas	Principals	School Heads	Schools In Charge
Public Elementary Schools			
CD 1	5	5	5
CD 2	5	5	5
CD 3	5	5	5
Total	15	15	15

In selecting the participants, the researcher ensured that those invited had substantial involvement in the operations of Learning Resource Centers within their

respective schools. Priority was given to individuals who could provide rich, relevant insights based on their roles and experiences. The selection process was guided not only by the inclusion criteria but also by the recommendations of district supervisors who were familiar with the professional capabilities and responsibilities of potential participants. This approach helped ensure that the data gathered would be both credible and reflective of actual practices within the established LRCs.

Research Instrument

The researcher conducted an interview as the primary tool for gathering data. Before the actual conduct of the study, the researcher prepared an interview guide based on the questions stated in the statement of the problem. This interview guide was used in the interview of the administrators such as principals, school heads, and the school in charge.

Research Procedure

The researcher first secured permission from the Dean of the Graduate School at Holy Name University in Tagbilaran City, Bohol. The questionnaires were distributed to all randomly selected principals, head teachers, and school in-charge respondents. The respondents were requested to answer thoroughly and assured their responses would be kept confidential. They were also informed that thoughtful responses significantly impact the validity of the data collected. The responses were used as data necessary for the statistical analysis and accurate quantitative tally of results. After data collection, the data will be tabulated for presentation, analysis, and interpretation in line with the purpose of the study.

Data Analysis

In this study, a qualitative approach was utilized to comprehensively gather and analyze data through interviews, and reflexive thematic analysis was employed. This approach involved arranging responses logically or chronologically, identifying and clustering themes into meaningful groups, examining specific documents, occurrences, and instances for their relevance to the study, and identifying patterns.

RESULTS

This chapter presents the analysis and interpretation of data gathered from interviews with school administrators on the development, challenges, and sustainability of Learning Resource Centers (LRCs). The data were analyzed using thematic analysis and categorized for clarity.

Table 1. Schools' Initiation in the Development of Learning Resource Centers

Theme	Schools' Initiation
Motivation for Establishment	School administrators initiated LRC development to address limited learning resources and create an environment conducive to student learning. Despite the absence of government funding, they viewed it as a long-term investment in education.
Initial Steps Taken	Administrators conducted needs assessments, consulted teachers and parents, developed proposals, and secured initial resources before launching the LRC.
Resource Acquisition Strategies	Schools used fundraising events, partnerships with local businesses and NGOs, and book donation drives to gather financial and material support.
Space Utilization and Adaptation	Due to limited infrastructure, administrators repurposed storage rooms, vacant classrooms, and multi-use spaces to house the LRC.

Table 1 shows the initiatives taken by school administrators to establish Learning Resource Centers (LRCs) despite financial and logistical challenges.

Theme 1: Motivation for Establishment

The motivation behind the establishment of Learning Resource Centers (LRCs) stemmed from school administrators' recognition of the need for accessible learning resources that could enhance student academic performance. Many administrators noted that limited access to books, technology, and other educational materials hindered student learning and that establishing an LRC was a way to address these gaps. Despite the absence of government funding, they viewed the initiative as a long-term investment in improving their schools' overall quality of education.

One administrator highlighted the importance of taking the initiative: "Students lacked a place where they could read, study, or conduct research. Instead of waiting for additional funding, we decided to establish a learning resource center using whatever resources we could gather." Another school leader echoed this sentiment, who explained, "We knew that having an LRC would provide better support for students, so we prioritized its development despite the financial and logistical challenges."

Administrators perceived LRCs as essential in fostering independent learning, research skills, and academic improvement. According to Barrett et al. (2019), the availability of well-equipped resource centers and quality school infrastructure positively impacts students' academic performance, especially in areas with limited access to

educational materials. Similarly, Arifin (2020) emphasized that critical reading plays a vital role in enhancing students' reading comprehension and critical thinking skills, underlining the importance of establishing learning resource centers that support such activities.

Given these benefits, school leaders took proactive steps in establishing LRCs, even when faced with funding and resource limitations. Recent research by Hua et al. (2024) found that self-directed learning experiences significantly enhance student engagement and satisfaction, particularly in blended learning environments, highlighting the importance of promoting independent learning spaces within schools.

Theme 2: Initial Steps Taken

Before officially launching an LRC, school administrators engaged in a series of preparatory steps to ensure its successful development. One of the first steps was conducting a needs assessment to determine which resources were most essential for students and teachers. Administrators consulted teachers, parents, and stakeholders to identify the primary challenges in accessing learning materials and to gather insights on the most effective way to structure the LRC.

One respondent explained, "Before setting up the LRC, we conducted surveys and held meetings with teachers and parents to understand what students needed most, whether it was more books, computers, or simply a quiet study area." This collaborative approach ensured that the LRC would be responsive to the academic needs of students rather than just a generic reading space.

The role of stakeholder consultation in educational program development has been widely emphasized in literature. Bunijevac (2017) emphasized that educational initiatives are more effective and sustainable when teachers, parents, and students are actively involved in the planning and implementation processes, highlighting the value of collaborative engagement in educational reform. Similarly, Rudo and Dimock (2017) stated that meaningful involvement of families, schools, and communities, particularly when aligned with student needs, can significantly improve student achievement and strengthen the impact of school programs such as learning resource centers.

After the assessment, administrators worked on developing proposals and securing initial resources to launch the center. Some schools formulated project plans to seek financial and material support from local businesses, non-profits, and government units. Others partnered with teachers and parents to collect book donations and gather essential materials. A school leader noted, "We started small, with just a few books and chairs. Over time, as we received more support, we expanded our collection and improved the space."

The collaborative and strategic approach taken by school administrators in the initial stages of LRC development ensured that the project was well-organized, sustainable, and aligned with student needs.

Theme 3: Resource Acquisition Strategies

Given the lack of government funding, school administrators relied on alternative strategies to acquire books, computers, and other essential resources for the LRC. One of the most common methods used was fundraising through school and community events. Schools organized raffles, benefit concerts, and other activities to raise money for LRC development.

A school head shared, "Since we couldn't rely on government funds, we looked for alternative ways to gather resources. Fundraising events allowed us to buy books and improve the learning center step by step." Some administrators also reached out to local businesses and corporate sponsors, securing donations of books, furniture, and even technology like second-hand computers.

The effectiveness of fundraising and community-based initiatives has been highlighted in studies. Hickman (2009) found that schools that engage local businesses and non-profit organizations in fundraising efforts are more likely to sustain educational programs. Similarly, Bryk and Schneider (2002) emphasized that strong community ties enable schools to receive consistent financial and material support for learning initiatives.

Another key approach was building partnerships with NGOs and educational foundations that supported literacy and learning initiatives. Some schools were able to secure grant funding and book donations from non-profit organizations, significantly boosting their LRC collections. One administrator noted, "We partnered with a literacy organization that donated hundreds of books. This was a game-changer in making the LRC fully functional."

Additionally, alumni networks played a role in resource acquisition, with former students contributing books and financial assistance. Administrators emphasized that community engagement was crucial in sustaining the LRC, as it allowed for continuous resource expansion without relying solely on government funding.

The effectiveness of fundraising, partnerships, and community involvement demonstrated that even with financial constraints, strategic resource acquisition efforts enabled schools to develop and maintain functional LRCs.

Theme 4: Space Utilization and Adaptation

One of the biggest logistical challenges in establishing an LRC was the lack of available space in schools. Many administrators noted that their schools did not have dedicated rooms for learning centers, forcing them to repurpose existing spaces such as storage rooms, vacant classrooms, and multi-use facilities.

A respondent described how their school adapted to the situation: "We had no spare rooms, so we cleaned out an old storage area and converted it into an LRC. It wasn't perfect, but it gave students a place to read and study." Similarly, another school head explained, "We initially set up the LRC in the faculty lounge, but as we expanded, we were able to relocate it to a dedicated space." These examples highlight the flexibility and resourcefulness of administrators in maximizing the available infrastructure.

Barrett et al. (2019) highlighted the importance of flexible and well-designed school infrastructure in supporting student learning outcomes, emphasizing that adaptive use of space plays a key role in educational effectiveness. Similarly, Kim and Jang (2020) noted that in underserved schools, utilizing multi-functional areas and integrating sustainable technology significantly improve resource accessibility and support the continuity of educational programs.

To optimize limited space, some schools implemented mobile learning centers, where books and study materials were kept on mobile shelves and moved around as needed. Others shared space with libraries, faculty lounges, or computer rooms, ensuring that students could still access the LRC even if a dedicated room was not available.

Despite these limitations, administrators remained committed to improving the space over time. One school head shared, "We started with a small area, but as support grew, we were able to renovate and create a better environment for students." Schools prioritized functionality and accessibility, ensuring that the LRCs remained a welcoming and effective learning space despite infrastructure constraints.

Table 2. Internal and External Support for LRC Development

Theme	Internal and External Support
Internal Support from Teachers and Students	Teachers volunteered to manage the LRC, while student assistants were assigned to help with organization and daily operations.
Community Involvement	Schools engaged parents, the PTA, and community members in fundraising, book drives, and LRC setup efforts.
Local Government Assistance	Some schools received financial support and logistical assistance from LGUs, but

	engagement was inconsistent across institutions.
Corporate and Non-Profit Contributions	Partnerships with businesses, universities, and NGOs provided schools with donated books, technology, and funding.

Table 3 shows the various forms of support received by schools for the establishment and maintenance of Learning Resource Centers (LRCs). This includes internal support from teachers, students, and school staff, as well as external contributions from parents, local government units (LGUs), and community organizations.

Theme 1: Internal Support from Teachers and Students

The role of teachers and students in maintaining Learning Resource Centers (LRCs) is critical to their functionality and sustainability. Given the limited availability of dedicated staff for LRC management, many schools relied on volunteer teachers and student assistants to oversee daily operations. Teachers played an essential role in managing resources, organizing materials, and guiding students on how to effectively use the LRC.

One administrator emphasized the significance of teacher involvement, stating, "Since we do not have permanent staff assigned to the LRC, our teachers take turns managing it. They help monitor book usage and ensure that students maximize available resources." Similarly, student assistants provided support in organizing materials, maintaining order, and assisting their peers in utilizing the LRC effectively.

Chien (2016) emphasized that the establishment and effective management of teaching resource centers promote practical teaching methods and lifelong learning. By actively involving both teachers and students in the use and maintenance of these centers, schools can enhance learner engagement, foster a culture of responsibility, and sustain operations even in the face of staffing limitations.

Theme 2: Community Involvement

The participation of parents, the PTA, and community members was instrumental in supporting LRC development. Many schools engaged parents in fundraising activities, book drives, and volunteer initiatives to help expand LRC resources. The Parent-Teacher Association (PTA) played a particularly crucial role by organizing financial contributions, assisting in material acquisition, and advocating for resource center improvements.

One school head shared, "The PTA helped us secure books through donation drives and fundraisers. Their efforts allowed us to expand our LRC collection significantly." Another administrator emphasized, "We reached out to the community for support, and

some members volunteered to donate books and educational materials." These community-driven initiatives provided additional resources for LRCs, reducing reliance on government funding.

Studies highlight the importance of community engagement in sustaining educational programs. Hickman (2008) found that schools with active parental involvement are more likely to develop well-equipped learning centers. Similarly, Bryk and Schneider (2002) emphasized that strong school-community partnerships improve access to educational resources and enhance student learning experiences. Schools that effectively engaged parents and the community in LRC development secured greater financial and material support, ensuring the center's continuous improvement.

Theme 3: Local Government Assistance

Local government units (LGUs) provided financial support and logistical assistance for LRCs, although the level of involvement varied across schools. Some administrators reported receiving funding from municipal or barangay officials, while others struggled to gain consistent support from local authorities.

One respondent explained, "We were fortunate that our barangay provided funds for books and minor renovations in our LRC." However, another school head highlighted the inconsistency of LGU support, stating, "Not all schools receive equal attention from the local government. Some get funding, while others have to rely entirely on external sources."

This disparity in local government engagement aligns with the findings of Landico and Amada (2021), who emphasized that stakeholder satisfaction, including support from local government units, plays a critical role in the enhancement and sustainability of student support services. Their study suggests that strong LGU involvement contributes significantly to the effectiveness of school-based learning initiatives, including the development and maintenance of Learning Resource Centers (LRCs).

While some schools benefited from financial and logistical assistance from LGUs, others had to seek alternative means of funding. Strengthening government support through policy advocacy and school-LGU collaboration is essential to ensure equitable LRC development across institutions.

Theme 4: Corporate and Non-Profit Contributions

In addition to government and community support, businesses, universities, and NGOs played a crucial role in donating books, technology, and funding for LRCs. Many schools partnered with private organizations through corporate social responsibility (CSR) programs, securing much-needed educational materials.

One administrator noted, "We partnered with a local business that donated computers for our LRC, which helped students access digital resources." Similarly, some schools collaborated with NGOs focused on literacy and education, receiving book donations and training for teachers on resource center management. Another school head stated, "An education-focused NGO provided us with reading materials and even facilitated workshops on maximizing our LRC."

Research supports the role of external collaboration and strategic design in enhancing school development. Johnson and Lomas (2005) emphasized that well designed learning spaces developed in partnership with stakeholders can significantly influence student engagement and learning outcomes. Their study highlights how thoughtful integration of design and learning principles, often supported by external organizations, contributes to more sustainable and effective educational environments.

By leveraging partnerships with businesses and NGOs, schools were able to expand their LRC collections, improve technological access, and enhance the overall learning environment. These external contributions played a vital role in ensuring that students had access to diverse and high-quality educational resources.

Table 3. Challenges in Establishing Learning Resource Centers

Theme	Specific Challenges
Financial Constraints	Lack of local government funding for the Learning Resource Center
	Dependence on external donations and sponsorships
	Difficulty in securing grants and financial assistance
Operational Challenges	Limited availability of books, computers, and study materials
	Insufficient number of school personnel to manage the center
	High dependency on volunteers for center maintenance
	Space limitations for setting up the Learning Resource Center
Stakeholder Engagement Issues	Low involvement of barangay LGUs and stakeholders
	Limited parent and community support in resource generation
	Inconsistent participation in school-led initiatives

Table 3 shows the key challenges faced by schools in establishing Learning Resource Centers (LRCs).

Theme 1: Financial Constraints

The lack of government funding emerged as one of the most significant challenges in establishing Learning Resource Centers (LRCs). Across various schools, administrators emphasized that financial limitations restricted their ability to acquire essential learning materials, integrate technology, and enhance the infrastructure necessary for effective resource centers. The absence of direct government support for LRC development compelled school leaders to seek alternative funding sources to sustain their initiatives.

One school head expressed a strong commitment to providing a lasting impact on students despite financial barriers, stating, "Even without local funding, I knew a resource center would have a long-lasting impact on student success. However, we had to rely heavily on fundraising and community efforts without government financial support." This sentiment was echoed by another administrator who shared that without allocated government resources, schools had to explore various creative financial strategies. "The absence of government allocation for LRC development meant that we had to be creative in securing financial resources. We conducted fundraising events, solicited donations from alumni, and reached out to corporate sponsors." These statements underscore the proactive measures taken by school administrators in addressing financial constraints, demonstrating the necessity of community-driven efforts in sustaining LRCs.

Financial constraints remain a major challenge in making school library learning resource centers effective, particularly in low-resource environments. Chandrasekhar (2018) found that limited budgets directly affect the availability and quality of learning materials, making it difficult for schools to establish and sustain well-functioning resource centers. As a result, school administrators often carry the responsibility of seeking external support and initiating local partnerships to bridge the funding gap and meet the learning needs of their students.

Further studies reinforce the importance of financial support in enhancing learning environments. Rittidet et al. (2009) emphasized that sustainable financial investment is essential for the success of community and school-based learning centers, particularly in providing access to alternative learning opportunities for the youth. Their research highlights how inadequate funding often leads to limited educational resources, delayed program implementation, and inconsistent access to learning materials, all of which hinder academic progress and overall student development.

Financial constraints remain a significant hurdle in the establishment and sustainability of Learning Resource Centers. While government funding remains

inadequate, school administrators have displayed resilience and innovation in securing alternative resources to support their educational initiatives. Through community-driven efforts, fundraising campaigns, and strategic partnerships, schools have been able to partially mitigate the financial challenges associated with LRC development. However, long-term solutions—such as increased government investment and policy reforms—are essential to ensure the continuous growth and accessibility of learning resource centers in educational institutions.

Theme 2: Operational Challenges

The establishment of Learning Resource Centers (LRCs) posed significant operational challenges for school administrators, particularly regarding staffing, space allocation, and workload management. Many administrators struggled to designate personnel exclusively for LRC operations, as teachers were already burdened with their teaching responsibilities. One school head explained, "One of our major problems was staffing. Since teachers were already overloaded with classes, assigning someone to manage the LRC full-time was nearly impossible." Without dedicated staff, resource center management often became inconsistent, limiting its accessibility and effectiveness.

Another major challenge was the lack of dedicated space for the LRC. Many schools lacked available classrooms or offices, forcing administrators to convert storage rooms or shared spaces into makeshift learning centers. One school head shared, "We struggled with space allocation. The school didn't have an extra room for a Learning Resource Center, so we had to repurpose an old storage room and gradually improve it over time." While this strategy provided students with access to learning materials, it compromised the quality of the space, as other school activities often disrupted it.

Aside from staffing and space constraints, administrators faced overlapping responsibilities, which affected their ability to effectively oversee LRC operations. Balancing administrative duties, faculty concerns, and school programs while managing the LRC placed an additional burden on school leaders. One administrator stated, "Managing a Learning Resource Center alongside daily administrative tasks is difficult. Balancing regular duties, faculty concerns, and school programs while trying to set up a sustainable LRC requires extreme dedication." These competing priorities delayed LRC implementation and made long-term sustainability challenging.

Masnawati and Darmawan (2022) highlighted that effective educational leadership plays a crucial role in managing school resources and improving organizational performance. They emphasized that in resource-limited environments, school administrators often face challenges in allocating space and personnel for additional learning programs, which can lead to operational inefficiencies. Without structured delegation, clear staffing assignments, and strategic space planning, facilities

such as Learning Resource Centers (LRCs) risk being underutilized or inconsistently managed.

The operational challenges of staffing shortages, space limitations, and workload pressures significantly impact the sustainability of Learning Resource Centers. While administrators have attempted to repurpose spaces and integrate LRC management into existing roles, these solutions may not be sustainable long-term. To ensure that LRCs remain functional and accessible, schools require government-supported staffing allocations, infrastructure investments, and policy interventions to support effective resource center management.

Theme 3: Stakeholder Engagement Issues

Stakeholder involvement is crucial for the successful implementation of school-based initiatives, particularly in the development and sustainability of Learning Resource Centers (LRCs). However, many school heads faced difficulties in securing active participation from barangay LGUs, parents, and the broader community. The lack of consistent stakeholder engagement hindered resource generation and limited the overall impact of the LRC on student learning.

One administrator expressed frustration over the minimal involvement of local government units (LGUs), stating, "We expected strong support from the local government, but their involvement was minimal. They didn't prioritize educational projects, which left us to find alternative funding sources." Despite the crucial role of LGUs in supporting school programs, many administrators found themselves relying on external sponsorships and community-driven efforts to sustain the LRC.

Parental engagement was also inconsistent, with some parents actively contributing to school initiatives while others remained disengaged. One school head noted, "Parental involvement was inconsistent. Some parents actively participated in book drives, but others were disengaged, believing that learning resources should be the sole responsibility of the school." This lack of uniform participation created challenges in mobilizing resources, as schools could not fully depend on parents for financial or material support.

Community engagement plays a pivotal role in the sustainability of educational programs. Bryk and Schneider (2002) emphasized that schools with strong partnerships with local stakeholders are more likely to develop effective, long-term educational programs. Similarly, Hickman (2008) noted that limited stakeholder participation can hinder the development of school-based resources, affecting both accessibility and sustainability. Schools that fail to establish strong collaborative relationships with stakeholders often struggle to secure consistent funding, donations, and volunteer support.

The challenges in engaging LGUs, parents, and the community underscore the need for structured stakeholder collaboration strategies. Schools must actively strengthen partnerships through outreach programs, transparent communication, and shared decision-making to ensure that Learning Resource Centers receive the necessary support. Sustainable engagement requires collective responsibility, wherein government units, parents, and the local community work together to enhance educational opportunities for students.

Table 4. Respondents' Recommendations to Enhance Learning Resource Centers

Theme	Recommendations
Requesting Small Financial Assistance	Ask barangay officials and school heads for small funding to buy bookshelves or chairs. Organize a simple reading campaign or donation drive to collect second-hand books.
Encouraging Parental and Alumni Support	Involve PTA members in book donation initiatives or minor LRC repairs. Request alumni to donate used books, old magazines, or simple educational posters for the LRC.
Repurposing Unused Spaces for LRC	Convert a small corner of a classroom or an old stockroom into a mini-LRC. Seek help from the school maintenance staff to repaint walls or install makeshift shelves.
Utilizing Available Digital Resources	Use existing school tablets or faculty computers for research in the LRC. Download free worksheets or e-books and print them for student use.
Assigning LRC Responsibilities to Teachers and Students	Designate a teacher-librarian to oversee the LRC on a weekly schedule. Assign student assistants to help organize books and maintain cleanliness.

Table 4 shows the recommendations provided by school administrators, teachers, and supervisors to improve Learning Resource Centers (LRCs).

Theme 1: Requesting Small Financial Assistance

One of the most significant challenges in establishing LRCs is limited funding, making it difficult for schools to acquire books, furniture, and other essential materials. To address this, respondents suggested seeking small-scale financial assistance from barangay officials and school heads to fund essential items such as bookshelves and chairs. Since government funding for LRCs is often inconsistent or insufficient, schools

must also organize simple donation drives and reading campaigns to encourage book donations from teachers, parents, and students.

A school principal shared, "Since we don't have an allocated budget for the LRC, we reached out to our barangay officials for assistance. They provided some funds that allowed us to buy bookshelves and additional seating for students."

Cruz and Ormilla (2022) emphasized the role of local government units in supporting public elementary schools through various initiatives, including disaster risk reduction and preparedness programs. Their findings suggest that even small scale assistance from local stakeholders can significantly improve school environments and operational readiness. This highlights the broader potential of community collaboration and alternative funding sources, such as locally initiated projects and resource mobilization efforts, in enhancing school facilities like Learning Resource Centers (LRCs), especially in underserved areas.

Schools can gradually improve their LRC facilities without waiting for large-scale funding allocations by securing modest financial assistance and organizing low-cost fundraising activities.

Theme 2: Encouraging Parental and Alumni Support

Community involvement, particularly from parents and alumni, is crucial in enhancing and sustaining LRCs. Respondents recommended involving PTA members in book donation initiatives and minor LRC repairs to reduce reliance on external funding. Alumni were also identified as valuable contributors, as they can donate used books, educational posters, and school materials to expand LRC resources.

One teacher noted, "We asked parents to donate books their children no longer use, and we were able to fill several shelves in our LRC. Some alumni also provided used educational magazines, which helped improve our reading materials."

Research supports the idea that parental and alumni engagement leads to better educational resource development. Bryk and Schneider (2002) found that schools with strong parental involvement are likelier to have well-equipped learning centers due to consistent material and financial contributions. Hickman (2008) further emphasized that alumni networks are an underutilized resource for school improvements, as many former students are willing to contribute to programs that benefit future generations.

Encouraging active participation from parents and alumni ensures that LRCs receive ongoing material and financial support, allowing them to expand their collections and improve facilities.

Theme 3: Repurposing Unused Spaces for LRC

Space constraints are a common issue in many schools, with no dedicated rooms available for LRCs. Respondents suggested converting small, underutilized spaces—such as storage rooms, old classrooms, or vacant faculty areas—into functional reading spaces. To minimize costs, they also recommended seeking help from school maintenance staff or parent volunteers for basic renovations, such as repainting walls and installing bookshelves.

One administrator shared, "We had no spare rooms for an LRC, so we cleaned out an old stockroom and turned it into a small reading space. Parents helped repaint the walls, and teachers donated bookshelves."

Hayashi et al. (2023) emphasized the value of adaptive space utilization in enhancing learning experiences. Their case study revealed that thoughtful modifications to learning environments, such as reorganizing furniture and adjusting seating arrangements, can significantly improve student engagement and collaboration. These findings support the importance of transforming underutilized school spaces into functional and inviting learning areas through small scale, practical interventions.

By maximizing available space and repurposing existing areas, schools can create accessible and functional LRCs without requiring additional construction or major funding.

Theme 4: Utilizing Available Digital Resources

With limited physical books and learning materials, respondents recommended integrating free digital resources to supplement LRC collections. Schools with existing computers or tablets can set up a small digital reading area, while those with limited technology access can download and print free e-books and worksheets for students.

A teacher explained, "We downloaded free PDF books and printed copies for students who didn't have access to online resources. This helped them explore more reading materials beyond what was physically available in our LRC."

Research highlights the benefits of digital integration in school resource centers. Bond and Bedenlier (2019) emphasized that the integration of educational technology in school environments significantly enhances student engagement by offering interactive and flexible access to learning content. Their study supports the idea that digital resources, when thoughtfully implemented in school resource centers, can expand educational opportunities and promote independent learning among students.

By leveraging free digital resources and using available technology, schools can expand LRC offerings without incurring high costs.

Theme 5: Assigning LRC Responsibilities to Teachers and Students

To ensure the sustainability of LRCs, respondents suggested assigning clear roles to teachers and students. Schools without full-time librarians can designate a teacher-in-charge on a rotating schedule to oversee book organization, resource management, and student engagement. Additionally, appointing student assistants to help maintain LRC cleanliness and organization fosters a sense of ownership and responsibility.

A school head shared, "We created a simple system where teachers take turns supervising the LRC, and student volunteers help in organizing books and keeping the space clean."

Studies support the effectiveness of teacher and student involvement in resource center management. Magulod Jr. (2019) emphasized that students who develop consistent study habits and actively engage with academic resources are more likely to perform better in their coursework. His findings suggest that involving students in the management and upkeep of learning resource centers can foster a sense of responsibility, reinforce positive study behaviors, and enhance their appreciation for educational materials. This supports the broader view that student participation is a valuable component in sustaining effective learning environments.

By assigning structured roles to teachers and students, schools can ensure that LRCs remain well-maintained, organized, and accessible to all learners.

Findings

The study revealed the following findings:

- 1. Schools' Initiatives in the Development of LRCs.** Findings revealed that public schools in Bohol took proactive measures to develop Learning Resource Centers (LRCs) despite financial and logistical constraints. School administrators recognized the importance of LRCs in enhancing student access to learning materials and took the initiative to establish them even with limited government support. Before launching the LRCs, schools conducted needs assessments to determine resource gaps and collaborated with teachers, parents, and stakeholders to identify the most pressing needs. To address funding limitations, many schools organized fundraising activities, book drives, and formed partnerships with local businesses and NGOs to acquire books and other educational materials. Due to infrastructure constraints, some schools repurposed underutilized spaces, such as storage rooms or vacant classrooms, to serve as LRCs, ensuring students had a dedicated space for learning and research.

- 2. Internal and External Support for LRC Development.** The study found that strong collaboration between internal and external stakeholders was crucial in sustaining the Learning Resource Center (LRC) operations. Teachers and students actively participated, with volunteer teachers managing daily operations and student assistants maintaining cleanliness. Parents, PTAs, and community members contributed through book donations, fundraising, and minor renovations. Some schools received small-scale financial assistance from barangay and municipal officials, though support varied. Additionally, alumni and private organizations provide books, furniture, and second-hand computers, expanding LRC resources and improving student access to learning materials.
- 3. Challenges in Establishing LRCs.** Despite efforts to develop Learning Resource Centers (LRCs), schools faced several significant challenges. Limited funding made it difficult to acquire books, digital materials, and basic furniture, forcing schools to rely on donations and alternative fundraising methods. Inconsistent stakeholder engagement also posed a problem, as some PTAs, barangay officials, and local government units provided minimal or irregular support. Additionally, space constraints required administrators to convert small storage rooms or shared areas into makeshift LRCs, which were often inadequate for student needs. Schools also struggled with a shortage of updated books and digital learning resources, limiting students' access to quality materials and hindering the effectiveness of LRCs.
- 4. Respondents' Recommendations to Enhance LRCs.** Based on the challenges identified, school supervisors, principals, and teachers suggested realistic and achievable strategies to improve Learning Resource Centers (LRCs). They recommended requesting small-scale funding from barangay officials and school heads to purchase essential items such as bookshelves and seating. Strengthening parental and alumni support through book donation drives and engaging the PTA in minor LRC repairs was also emphasized. Schools were encouraged to repurpose existing spaces, such as old stockrooms or classroom corners, into functional reading areas to maximize limited infrastructure. To address the shortage of learning materials, respondents suggested utilizing available digital resources, including free e-books, printable worksheets, and repurposed school computers. Lastly, ensuring sustainable LRC management through the assignment of teacher-librarians and student volunteers was seen as a practical solution to maintain order and accessibility in LRCs.

Conclusions

Learning Resource Centers (LRCs) are essential in schools, providing students with better access to educational materials and promoting independent learning. However, financial and logistical constraints often hinder their development and sustainability. School administrators, teachers, and students are crucial in establishing

and managing LRCs, as their volunteerism and proactive efforts ensure that these learning spaces remain functional despite challenges.

Stakeholders' involvement plays a significant role in LRC sustainability, with schools that receive consistent support from PTAs, alumni, and local government units being better equipped to maintain and improve LRC services. Given space and resource limitations, innovative solutions such as repurposing existing spaces, maximizing digital resources, and implementing community-driven initiatives allow schools to develop functional and sustainable LRCs even with minimal funding. Sustainability measures such as structured LRC management, teacher and student involvement, and continuous community engagement must be implemented to ensure long-term success.

Recommendations

Based on the study's comprehensive findings and insightful conclusions, the following recommendations are proposed to enhance the development, sustainability, and management of Learning Resource Centers (LRCs) in public schools. These recommendations aim to address the challenges identified, strengthen stakeholder support, optimize resource utilization, and ensure the long-term functionality of LRCs.

- 1. Establishing a Sustainable Resource Mobilization Plan.** Schools should develop a structured resource mobilization plan to sustain LRC development. This may include forming committees responsible for securing donations, organizing book drives, and initiating local partnerships. Schools can also integrate income-generating projects, such as school-based literacy campaigns or community reading programs, to fund LRC improvements. Strengthening collaborations with local businesses and non-government organizations (NGOs) will further help in acquiring essential books, furniture, and technology.
- 2. Enhancing Stakeholder Engagement and Support.** PTAs, parents, and alumni should be actively involved in LRC development by contributing books, supporting minor renovations, and assisting in fundraising efforts. Strengthening partnerships with local businesses, NGOs, and community organizations can provide additional funding and resources. Encouraging barangay officials and local government units to allocate funds for LRC maintenance and improvements will further ensure sustainability.
- 3. Maximizing Space Utilization for LRCs.** Given space constraints in many schools, administrators should continue repurposing underutilized areas, such as storage rooms, vacant classrooms, or multi-use spaces, into functional LRCs. Schools may also explore the use of modular or mobile learning spaces to accommodate more students. Minor renovations, such as repainting and installing bookshelves, should be supported through school maintenance teams and community volunteers.

- 4. Expanding Learning Resources Through Digital Integration.** To address the shortage of updated books, schools should integrate digital learning resources, including free e-books, printable worksheets, and repurposed school computers. Teachers should be encouraged to incorporate digital tools in their lessons and guide students in utilizing available technology for research and independent learning. Schools should also explore partnerships with universities and libraries for shared digital access to academic materials.
- 5. Ensuring Sustainable LRC Management and Operations.** A structured LRC management system should be implemented, with teacher-librarians assigned on a rotational basis to oversee daily operations. Student volunteers should be trained to assist in organizing books, maintaining cleanliness, and managing borrowing systems. Regular assessment and monitoring should be conducted to ensure that LRCs remain functional and continuously improve to meet student learning needs.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The protocol before the study's conduct was observed correctly. The researcher underwent the Research Ethics Committee review procedures and secured the "Clearance to Gather Data" before conducting the interviews to ensure that the process was following the appropriate ethical standards. After the proposal hearing, the research manuscript was submitted to the Holy Name University's Ethics Review Board for evaluation and approval. The researcher adhered to the highest ethical standards in conducting the study.

Before the interviews, all participants were provided with an informed consent form outlining the objectives of the study, their rights as participants, and the assurance of anonymity and confidentiality. The form clearly emphasized that participation was entirely voluntary and that participants had the right to withdraw or discontinue their involvement at any point without any consequences. Participants were given ample time to review and decide whether they agreed with the terms and conditions of the study.

Proper permission and consent were secured from the school administrators, who signed the consent forms to signify their willingness to participate as respondents. Throughout the study, the researcher ensured that the fundamental principles of ethical research were upheld, particularly in the handling of personal information and data privacy. Additionally, the study underwent an integrity test and citation audit to ensure academic honesty and to confirm that the manuscript was free from plagiarism.

Proposed Improvement Measures for the Development and Sustainability of Learning Resource Centers (LRCs) in Public Schools

Rationale

Learning Resource Centers (LRCs) play a critical role in enhancing student learning, promoting independent study habits, and improving access to educational materials. However, the findings of this study indicate that financial constraints, limited stakeholder engagement, space restrictions, and outdated learning materials hinder the effective establishment and sustainability of LRCs in public schools in Bohol. While schools have taken proactive initiatives, such as fundraising and space repurposing, the lack of structured resource mobilization and management strategies remains a challenge. To address these issues, this proposed improvement plan outlines concrete measures that focus on securing financial and material support, enhancing stakeholder participation, maximizing space utilization, integrating digital resources, and ensuring sustainable LRC management. These measures aim to create a well-functioning, resource-equipped LRC that serves as an accessible and effective learning environment for students.

Objectives

- To develop a sustainable resource mobilization plan to ensure continuous financial and material support for LRCs.
- To strengthen stakeholder engagement and collaboration among parents, PTAs, alumni, local businesses, and government units.
- To maximize available school spaces by repurposing underutilized areas into functional LRCs.
- To expand learning materials through the integration of digital and printed educational resources.
- To establish a structured management system for the long-term maintenance and improvement of LRCs.

Mechanics of Implementation

The implementation of these improvement measures will begin with the formation of an LRC Development Committee, which will be responsible for planning and overseeing all activities related to the enhancement of LRCs. This committee will include school administrators, teachers, PTA representatives, and student volunteers, ensuring a collaborative approach. Schools will seek financial and material support from local government units, alumni associations, and private organizations by submitting formal proposals and organizing community-based fundraising activities such as book fairs and reading campaigns. Additionally, schools will repurpose available spaces to establish functional LRCs and incorporate digital resources such as e-books and online learning platforms to supplement traditional materials. Teachers will receive training on LRC management strategies, and students will be encouraged to participate as volunteers to help maintain cleanliness and organize books.

Schedule of Implementation

The improvement plan will be implemented in phases over one academic year to allow for gradual development and evaluation. The first two months will focus on the formation of the LRC Development Committee, stakeholder consultations, and the identification of funding sources. By the third to fifth month, schools will initiate fundraising and resource mobilization activities while simultaneously repurposing spaces and acquiring necessary materials. From the sixth month onward, the LRCs will be fully operational, and monitoring mechanisms will be put in place to assess progress and effectiveness. Adjustments and improvements will be made based on continuous feedback from students, teachers, and stakeholders.

Monitoring and Evaluation System

The effectiveness of these improvement measures will be monitored through regular assessments and structured feedback mechanisms to ensure continuous development of the Learning Resource Centers (LRCs). The LRC Development Committee will lead quarterly evaluations that focus on key performance indicators such as the availability and accessibility of instructional materials, the degree of stakeholder involvement, and the frequency and quality of student utilization of the LRCs. These evaluations will be supplemented by surveys distributed to students and teachers, capturing their perceptions of the LRCs' usefulness, functionality, and overall impact on teaching and learning.

At the end of each academic year, a final comprehensive assessment will be carried out to evaluate the overall effectiveness of the implemented improvements. The findings from this year-end evaluation will serve as the basis for formulating data-driven recommendations and strategic enhancements that will guide the continued strengthening of LRC initiatives in the following school year.

Matrix

Areas of Concern	Objectives	Strategies	Person Involved	Time Frame	Success Indicators
Financial and Material Support	To develop a sustainable resource mobilization plan for continuous financial and material support.	Form an LRC Development Committee; Seek support from LGUs, NGOs, and alumni; Organize fundraising events such as book fairs and reading campaigns.	School Administrators, Teachers, PTA, Alumni, Local Government Units	First two months for committee formation, ongoing for resource mobilization.	Secured funding and materials; Increased availability of learning resources.
Stakeholder Engagement and Collaboration	To strengthen engagement among parents, PTAs, alumni, businesses, and local government.	Conduct stakeholder meetings and outreach programs; Establish donation drives; Engage	PTA, Alumni, Community Leaders, School Heads, Teachers, Local Businesses	Stakeholder meetings within the first quarter, continuous engagement throughout the year.	Active participation of stakeholders; Increased resource donations.

		community in literacy programs.			
Space Utilization and Optimization	To maximize available school spaces by repurposing underutilized areas into functional LRCs.	Identify and repurpose unused rooms; Conduct minor renovations; Use modular and mobile learning setups.	School Administrators, Maintenance Staff, PTA, Volunteer Teachers	Third to fifth month for space identification and renovation.	Fully functional LRCs; Increased student use of designated learning areas.
Integration of Digital Learning Resources	To expand learning materials through digital and printed educational resources.	Acquire second-hand computers and tablets; Download and print free e-books and worksheets; Partner with online learning platforms.	Teachers, IT Coordinators, School Heads, NGOs, University Partners	Ongoing throughout the school year.	Enhanced access to digital learning materials; Increased student engagement.
Sustainable LRC Management	To establish a structured management system for long-term maintenance and improvement.	Assign teacher-librarians and student volunteers; Implement book borrowing systems; Conduct quarterly LRC evaluations.	Teachers, Students, School Heads, LRC Committee	Sixth month onward for implementation, with regular evaluations.	Consistent maintenance of LRC; Efficient resource management; Increased student engagement.

By implementing these improvement measures, public schools in Bohol can develop sustainable and well-equipped LRCs that provide students with better access to educational materials, a conducive learning environment, and long-term academic benefits.

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